

THE IMPORTANCE OF RIDDLES, PROVERBS AND TONGUE TWISTERS IN UZBEK CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

This article depicts how the children's folklore effected to the Uzbek children's literature. This folklore is mainly associated with riddles, proverbs and tongue twisters. The main aim of this article is to determine the way of how these tools came into existence and the main function of them in the upbringing of the children.

Main body:

Riddles and puzzles. In ancient times, the Uzbek people attached great importance to the upbringing of their children to be strong, agile and intelligent. At that time, there were no schools to educate children. That is why people invented various games and other means. Children participating in games such as "Bekinmachoq" and "Chillak" began to develop physical qualities such as agility and dexterity. So, what should be done now to sharpen the minds of children? Mental games such as riddles and puzzles were created by the people in the process of searching for an answer to this question. The creator of the riddles is also the people.

On the surface, telling riddles between adults and children, between children and adults, seems like a hobby, not to get bored, but to pass the time quickly. In fact, riddles

are a way of thinking, through which the child can think and speak figuratively. Riddles help a child to increase vocabulary and develop speech. Teaching a child to find a riddle will lead to a gradual increase in thinking. So, one of the oldest and most active genres of folklore is to find. Riddles are closely connected with human, social life and natural phenomena and are always based on real reality. It reflects the various things in the material world that surround us. Each puzzle is an independent work with its own form and meaning. It reflects the essence of philosophical, historical, ethnographic symbols, concepts, events in the most beautiful, figurative expressions. This genre is performed in response to a puzzling question between two people or a team. The question part of traditional puzzles is puzzled by depicting, comparing, and simulating nature, natural phenomena, and each object in general in an artistic

way. The answer is to name the objects or natural phenomena that are enigmatic through the images, to find the meaning, to solve the hidden thing, to know.

It is noteworthy that each puzzle is closely linked with life. The find reflects the artistic and aesthetic aspects of the things around us, the traditions of the people. It helps to better understand the essence of existence, the essence of what is in it, by comparing and contrasting nature, natural phenomena and things.

One of the richest genres of folklore, the riddle consists of two parts, the main part of the riddle is to tell the name of the puzzle through the images. The question-and-puzzle part of it consists of puzzling nature, natural phenomena and objects, in general, by depicting, comparing and simulating the object in an artistic way. The answer to the puzzle part of the puzzle forms a whole in unity.

The riddle covers all things and events in existence, their various manifestations. Sky, blue, sun, moon, stars, natural phenomena; man and his organs; wildlife; birds, insects; trees, various plants, fruits, vegetables; household items; tools of labor, in general, have created many riddles about everything.

After all, the riddle has not lost its ideological and educational significance. Even today, new puzzles are being created about various things and events. Riddles, in particular, help children to develop their thinking skills, to express a certain idea in an artistic way, and to teach them intelligence and ingenuity. Good upbringing is about raising children as humane people who are ready to protect the weak at any time. In childhood, it begins with the protection of animals, and

even compassion for dragonflies, butterflies and flowers.

Suppose two children are standing in front of a window. The boy is two years old and the girl is four. They are watching the street with their noses in the mirror. Finally, looking out into the street, they grabbed the butterfly, which was hitting the glass, tore off its wings and began to watch it crawl. They found it very interesting. He used to fly, but now he is crawling.

"Daddy, mum," they said excitedly. "Come here and see!"

For some reason, his father did not want to watch their game.

"The butterfly's wings are just like your hands," he said. - Would it be good if a strong man played you like a butterfly? No one and nothing should be hurt.

Naturally, the children stare at each other, not knowing what to do. Then the father gets angry and reminds them of the nature that the children have studied before - the animals, birds, mammals, insects that do not kill, care for, reproduce, and so on. It would be nice if he could start telling interesting riddles.

Among pets, the most beloved and cherished of all is the cow. In any case, the cow is the breadwinner, helper of the family. If she is cared for and fed on time, she will be entertained with milk and cream. The riddle about him is also very surprising:

Early departure laylixon,
Laylikhon coming in the evening,
From various kindergartens,
Laylikhon is collecting.

Proverbs. Special attention is paid to the works of children's folklore, especially in the genre of proverbs, designed to educate children in the spirit of patriotism. Most of

the articles on this topic are introduced to the child before he or she goes to school. Often, the idea of loving and respecting the motherland for the children of this period is in the example of animals, birds and mammals.

There is happiness in the homeland; Born husband - homeland; The horse turns and finds the peg; A stateless man is a nightingale without a song; The horse of the lake is produced by fish; Fish live by water, man by hand; The garden of the nightingale is good, the mountain of the sparrow; Each plant has its own favorite soil; Each mare praises the spring from which she drinks; Every flower has its own scent, Every nation has its own color; The bird wants to leave, loves its hand, and so on.

Folk proverbs glorify goodness, honesty, truthfulness and honesty, and condemn evil, lies and deception. It is clear from the above comments that a person who uses the proverb of the people and lives in seven dimensions is never inferior. Thus, the genre of proverbs is developing and serves to develop children's consciousness.

Tongue twisters. One of the pillars of the great tower of human decency and the basis of humanity is to pierce the precious gem of speech and speech with gentleness and decency. Those who sit at the top of the

moral arch say that one of the highest ranks of human perfection and knowledge is beautiful speech and beautiful speech, the flower of this garden opens with the breeze of the first spring and can write a bright jewel of happiness only a merchant of the mind. The Greek rulers, whose pleasant and precious words are the crown of wisdom and ingenuity, say that language is the key to the treasure of every intelligent person, and the amount of knowledge of each person is determined by his words. A person should share his thoughts, achievements and joys, pains and sorrows with others. Being beautiful, burro, talking in pieces is also a skill, an art.

Conclusion: Proverbs and riddles are at the forefront of children's folklore. They are the result of the intellect of the people, of several generations, and of the experience of life, the product of their wisdom. They tell the story of a man of pure conscience, noble, industrious, who has tasted the bitterness of life, who has a rational view of life, and who draws conclusions from an event, a person, or a work. (for children) can serve as a guide. In particular, proverbs are created as an artistic expression of the people's intellect, socio-historical experience, struggle and labor.

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